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Experience in the remediation of mould infestation in a natural history collection

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Zusammenfassung

Wegen ungünstiger Klimaverhältnisse hatte sich im Jahr 2017 in Sammlungsräumen des Natur-Museums Luzern an Objekten aus allen Sammlungsbereichen bzw. an deren Aufbewahrungsbehälter Schimmel entwickelt. Da bei der Sanierung von Schimmelbefall einige Grundsätze zu berücksichtigen sind, wurde zusammen mit externen Fachleuten ein Konzept zur fachgerechten Eindämmung und Sanierung des Schimmels entwickelt. Die verschiedenen Schritte von den Sofortmassnahmen über die sorgfältige Evakuierung bis zur Reinigung werden in diesem Artikel vorgestellt.

Abstract

Due to unfavorable climatic conditions in collection rooms of the Natur-Museum Lucerne, mould developed on objects from all areas of the collection or on their storage containers. Since some principles have to be taken into account in the remediation of mould infestation, a concept for the professional containment and remediation of the mould was developed together with external experts. The various steps from immediate measures to careful evacuation to cleaning are presented in this article.

Starting position

In 2017, the Lucerne Natur-Museum housed a large part of its entomology, botany and vertebrate collection as well as its geological collection in temporary, external collection rooms, which were cooled and supplied with a portion of outside air. Due to unfavorable climatic conditions, mould could form on organic material over the summer months. Samples from the collections showed fungal colonies and spores of mould or black fungi of *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, *Penicillium sp.*, *Aspergillus terreus* and *Aspergillus glaucus*, which can grow at a relative humidity of 70-75% RH (RASCHLE 2017). Large areas of museum pieces and their collection containers as well as the floor and parts of the walls were infested. Due to the risk to people's health and to protect the affected buildings, it was necessary to remedy this level of pollution immediately (BAG 2009).

Immediate action

When remedying mould growth, there are a few basic principles that must be observed. Since moulds are microorganisms that threaten human health, great attention must be paid to health protection. Exposure to increased mould pollution can lead to irritation, allergic diseases or general feverish illnesses (SUVA leaflet). Drying out too quickly can increase the health risks and the damage to objects or buildings can increase under certain circumstances (BAG 2009). The contaminated collection rooms were therefore only entered with personal protective equipment (respiratory mask of type FFP2 or FFP3, protective suit, protective gloves, protective goggles).

When the humidity is reduced to 40% RH, mould comes under stress and produces large numbers of spores (GÜTEBIER 2012). In the worst case, this can lead to mould being

spread and neighbouring areas being contaminated. To prevent this, a company specialized in contamination remediation sealed off the affected rooms from the unpolluted ones. The areas were marked as «black» (contaminated) and «white» (unpolluted) and connected with locks (Fig. 1). As a further immediate measure, negative pressure maintenance systems (NPS) with HEPA filters of filter class 13 were set up in the black areas, and the cleaned exhaust air from the NPS was led away via provisionally set up exhaust ducts (Fig. 2). Only when there was negative pressure in the black rooms was the removal of the infected materials started.

Evacuation of the objects

Since it was not possible to clean the objects and the containers on site, all objects had to be evacuated from the collection rooms

and taken away to remove mould. However, there was not enough space available in the museum for this work, so external rooms had to be found. Thanks to the quick reaction of the real estate department of the Canton of Lucerne (Dienststelle Immobilien), free-standing, external rooms for the temporary storage and cleaning of the collections could be rented. When these rooms were prepared accordingly, the evacuation could begin.

Experts in protective equipment removed object by object or container after container from the racks in the collection rooms and brought them to the locks. There, other people in protective gear packed each piece individually in plastic bags and prepared it for removal. Finally someone in the white area took over the packed units, brought them to the transport vehicle and led them to the cleaning rooms.

Fig. 1: Between the contaminated and the unpolluted rooms, TRIPLEX panels on a wooden structure were used to create bulkheads with lock doors.

Fig. 2: Mobile negative pressure maintenance systems (NPS) with a separate exhaust air duct limited the mould load to the affected rooms and at the same time cleaned the room air.

Cleaning and return transport

At the cleaning site a distinction also had to be made between «black» areas, in which contaminated material was present, and «white», unpolluted areas. The two areas were also separated from each other with temporarily installed locks. Personnel in protective equipment worked in the black areas to remove the objects and containers from the plastic bags and to clean them with a vacuum cleaner with a water filter. In the lock, the cleaned pieces were received by another person and passed on for subsequent cleaning as required. Fortunately, in the majority of the botanical collections only the closed cardboard filing boxes were affected by mould. After the superficial vacuuming of the boxes, it was usually sufficient to replace them with new ones. In the earth sciences, too, the open cardboard collection boxes were replaced after the objects and object labels had been vacuumed. The wooden insect boxes of the entomology collection were cleaned with a vacuum cleaner and according to the experience of

THACKER ET. AL. (2008) additionally cleaned with 75% ethanol. The closed insect boxes had largely prevented mould from forming on insects inside. Nevertheless, a taxidermist had to clean individual affected insects by hand using a fine brush and a vacuum cleaner with a fine nozzle. The vertebrate specimens - primarily birds - were also cleaned individually by taxidermistic trained staff.

At the same time as the object cleaning, the collection rooms had to be renovated and thoroughly cleaned together with the object racks. Since the air conditioning had to be tested extensively, the cleaned material had to be temporarily stored at the cleaning site for several months. This required the establishment of temporary air conditioning and climate monitoring at this location too. After the completion of the renovation work, the museum's external collection rooms could finally be used again.

Fig. 3: The cleaning staff worked with respiratory protection hoods, protective gloves and disposable protective suits made of Tyvek, which were changed regularly.

Conclusion

Thanks to a careful, professional approach, the damage to the objects with mould infestation could be kept within narrow limits. The removal of the visible traces of mould was carried out very conscientiously and at great expense. Nevertheless, it was not possible to completely remove all the existing spores. Since short-term, higher humidity values above 60% RH could be sufficient to stimulate renewed mould growth (GÜTEBIER 2012), humidity values above this range should be absolutely avoided in future and increases in humidity should be detected at an early stage using suitable monitoring.

The planning of the individual renovation steps and the coordination of all those involved was a logistically demanding challenge, and the evacuation and cleaning of the objects were time-consuming, labour-intensive and costly. The replacement of storage material and the renovation and improvement of the collection rooms also resulted in high costs. It is therefore advisable to clarify the collection rooms for natural history objects very carefully before moving in, to observe the climatic conditions profoundly for a sufficiently long period of time before storing objects and to adjust the air conditioning if necessary.

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